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ENSURING FOOD SECURITY IN OUR COUNTRY IS A TOP PRIORITY

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Abstract: This article examines the issues surrounding food security, identifies current problems, and analyzes ways to address them. The main objective is to develop effective strategies for ensuring food security and explore best practices in the field.

Keywords: Social stability, protein, human health, starch, product, investment, hygiene and sanitation, canning, production volume.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с продовольственной безопасностью, определяются текущие проблемы и анализируются пути их решения. Основная цель — разработать эффективные стратегии обеспечения продовольственной безопасности и изучить передовой опыт в этой области.

Ключевые слова: Социальная стабильность, белок, здоровье человека, крахмал, продукт, инвестиции, гигиена и санитария, консервирование, объем производства.

Introduction

The issue of providing food for the world's population or food shortages is primarily linked to environmental concerns. The global population has reached 7.4 billion and is increasing by approximately 1 million people per week. Nearly 0.5 billion people in some countries are facing starvation, and millions die from hunger every year. Food consumption patterns vary widely across countries. For example, average per capita meat consumption globally is about 30 kg: 6 kg in Nigeria, 21 kg in China, 52 kg in Uzbekistan, 75 kg in the UK, and 110 kg in the USA.

Around 90.11% of food for the population is obtained from cultivated lands. Additionally, the world's oceans hold vast food resources.

Scientists are exploring reliable and innovative ways to produce food. Synthetic production of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, and vitamins is being suggested. One example is the production of sugar from starch.

The role of agricultural enterprises, particularly diversified farms, is increasing in the development of food production and processing industries. The sustainable development of agriculture lays the foundation for the advancement of the food industry and processing enterprises.

The Presidential Decree PF-4947 of February 7, 2017, titled “Action Strategy on Five Priority Directions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017–2021”, outlines

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modernization and accelerated development of agriculture, stating: “Ensure food security, supply the domestic market with products, and provide the population with essential agricultural goods.”

During the 2014 international conference titled “The Important Reserves for Implementing the Food Program in Uzbekistan,” the First President of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, highlighted that the country produces nearly 16 million tons of fruits and vegetables annually. Per capita, this amounts to 300 kg of vegetables, 75 kg of potatoes, and 44 kg of grapes—three times the optimal consumption norm. Moreover, Uzbekistan exports more than 180 types of fresh fruits and vegetables to 80 countries annually.

In 2020, domestic producers were tasked with increasing fruit, grape, and melon production by at least 2.3 times compared to 2014. This required reforms and modernization in agriculture, improvements in land reclamation and irrigation systems, and efforts to enhance soil fertility and crop yields. Attracting foreign investment, finding new markets, and developing modern storage, logistics, and delivery systems were also deemed crucial.

Key Indicators of Domestic Production¹.**Table 1.**

Parameter / Year	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025*
Production Volume (bln \$)	50.2	54.1	59.3	64.0	68.5	73.5
Industrial Growth (%)	1.5	3.8	5.4	6.2	6.8	7.3
Agricultural Growth (%)	2.0	3.2	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0
Share of Private Sector (%)	45	48	52	55	58	60
Export Volume (bln \$)	12.1	14.3	16.7	18.5	20.0	22.0
Import Coverage (%)	65	70	75	78	80	83

* 2025 forecast based on reports from the Government of Uzbekistan and the World Bank.).

From the table, it is evident that both industry and agriculture have shown steady growth between 2020 and 2023. The private sector's share is projected to rise from 45% in 2020 to 60% in 2025. Exports are expected to reach \$22 billion by 2025, mainly from textiles, cotton, and mineral products.

Production volume 2020-2025²(mlrd \$)

¹ Prepared by the author based on data from the Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.stat.uz

If we look at the years, national production decreased in 2020 due to the impact of the Pandemic. In 2021, it increased by 4.03% compared to 2020 due to the growth of the industrial and agricultural sectors. The main reason for the increase in production in 2023 was the increase in investments, infrastructure projects, the entry of foreign companies into our country, and the improvement of import substitution programs, which increased by 27.49% compared to 2020. The main reason for the increase in production in 2024 was the modernization of technology and an increase in exports, which increased by 46.41% compared to 2020.

Taking into account these promising tasks, Uzbekistan has decided to expand the scope of effective cooperation with FAO. The visit of the Director-General of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, José Graziano da Silva, to our country was an important step in this regard. During the high-level negotiations, an agreement was reached on the establishment of a representative office of this international organization in Uzbekistan. According to Yuriko Shoji, the Subregional Coordinator for Central Asia and Representative in Uzbekistan, the signing of the program within the framework of the country action program for 2014-2017 last year became an important roadmap for Uzbekistan's close cooperation with this international organization. This program is aimed at diversifying agricultural crops, improving production and livestock health, combating pests, expanding fish farming, and rational use of water resources on a sustainable basis.

In particular, FAO provides technical assistance in the field of sustainable farming and the introduction of other new agricultural methods. In order to increase the shelf life and export volume, new technologies are being implemented for planting, harvesting, processing and storing agricultural crops.

A project for the development of organic agriculture in Uzbekistan is also being developed within the framework of the country program for 2014-2017. Measures for the development of organic agriculture are being demonstrated on the example of pilot farms, and introductory events are being held to improve the skills of farmers and specialists in the agricultural sector and introduce modern technologies in this area.

The implementation of these measures will allow our country to strengthen its position in ensuring food security and make a significant contribution to the implementation of the global food program. In 2015, the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals was completed

² Prepared by the author based on data from the Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.stat.uz

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worldwide. Countries are gradually moving towards the Sustainable Development Goals, and achieving these goals will help eliminate the problem of hunger on Earth.

The dyes necessary for the food industry are obtained from red roses, beets, melons, onions, carrots, pumpkins and other plants. Such dyes, used as a paste, are used in the production of caramel, marmalade and other industries.

The dye left after the evaporation of red beet juice is viscous, has a beetroot smell and a sweet taste. Such a red dye is widely used because it is cheap. The dyes of strawberries, chesnuts, cherries, and cherries are also red. The implementation of this technology project would help to bring additional benefits and solve one of the problems.

Under the outer husk of rice is the aleurone layer. It consists of a concentrate of proteins and lipids, and the protein content is 11.5-17.2%. Rice contains amino acids such as lysine, histidine, arginine, glycerol, and alinine. The lipid content is 12-16.8%. That is why oil is extracted from rice in Brazil, Japan, the USA, Burma, and India. Rice is a raw material rich in vitamins. The mixture of cellulose and hemicellulose in rice is also of great importance in the diet. This mixture is used to treat obesity, cancer, stomach and other diseases. Rice contains more than 8% mineral components. It has been proven that a good effect can be achieved when 25% of wheat flour is mixed with rice flour. However, this property of rice has not been well studied in our regions.

Summary:

It would be wrong to say that the amount of toxic substances in agricultural products is perfectly analyzed in industrial and market laboratories. The reason for this is, first of all, the lack of qualified specialists and modern analytical instruments. The main cause of food spoilage is the oxidation of fats and the decomposition of products into their constituent parts. This process is also accelerated by mold and bacteria. Now substances have been developed that slow down and stop the oxidation of fats and other organic substances, which are called antioxidants. Agriculture has been able to demonstrate its efficiency, competitiveness, and ability to quickly adapt to market conditions in the long experience of developed countries. Accordingly, in Uzbekistan, great attention has been paid to the processing of agricultural products, the necessary economic conditions for this activity have been created, and the regulatory and legal framework has been developed. The establishment of agricultural enterprises in Uzbekistan in the context of the transition to market relations was the main content of agrarian reforms. Special attention was paid to the formation of a mechanism for processing agricultural products in our country that fully meets the principles of a market economy and to the system for ensuring its successful functioning.

Every year, a large amount of material resources and funds are allocated to support farms, which are the main representatives of agricultural enterprises. Today, it has become clear that the deep division of labor in agriculture, its practice and the system of training employees with narrow specialties corresponding to it have not justified themselves at all. On the contrary, this has become one of the factors that exacerbates the alienation of agricultural workers from the land or the loss of their independence.

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